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Overview of a Scientific Event

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Larysa Butko

Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Kremenchuk, Ukraine

Management of the Sphere of Culture: Creative and Innovative Vectors in the Conditions of Globalization Changes

On October 25–26, 2023, the annual VII International scientific and practical conference “Creative Technologies, Entrepreneurship and Management of the Organization of the Socio-Cultural Sphere of the 21st Century” was held at the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, organized by the Department of Fashion and Show Business¹.

The scientific event brought together representatives of foreign and domestic institutions of higher education that train cultural managers: University of Amsterdam (Netherlands), National-Louis University (Poland), Zhytomyr Ivan Ohiyenko Vocational College of Culture and Arts (Ukraine), Kyiv University of Culture (Ukraine), Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University (Ukraine), National Academy of Managerial Staff of Culture and Arts (Ukraine), Sumy State University (Ukraine), Szent István University (Hungary), University of Žilina (Slovakia), University of Extremadura (Spain), Mykolas Romeris University (Lithuania), University of Arts (USA), University of Trás-os-Montes (Portugal).

¹ Martynyshyn, Ya., & Khlystun, O., et al. (Eds.). (2023). *Kreatyvni Tekhnolohii, Pidpriemnytstvo i Menedzhment v Orhanizatsii Sotsio-Kul'turnoi Sfery XXI stolittia [Creative Technologies, Entrepreneurship and Management in the Organization of the Socio-Cultural Sphere of the 21st Century]*. Zbirnyk Materialiv VII Mizhnarodnoi Naukovo-Praktychnoi Konferentsii [Proceedings of the VII International Scientific and Practical Conference]. Kyiv: KNUKiM (in Ukr.). Retrieved from <https://drive.google.com/file/d/18Rv7pgq9sLPVgpNlipoTKpzLQg04AOF/view>

The participants of the conference had the opportunity to present scientific developments in the following thematic directions: current prospects for the development of the socio-cultural sphere: theory and practice; creative technologies and prospects for the development of the socio-cultural sphere: world trends and Ukrainian experience; modern management in the formation of the socio-cultural sphere of the 21st century; market relations, entrepreneurship and management in the fields of the socio-cultural sphere; state support of the socio-cultural sphere: resources, mechanisms, institutions. In the presented reports of scientific and pedagogical workers, practitioners and students of higher education, a comprehensive theoretical analysis and practical recommendations regarding the organization of management of the socio-cultural sphere in the conditions of powerful political, economic and social transformations of modern society were represented, such problematic issues were considered, such as: system analysis of modern management concepts; the most promising global management practices in the field of culture; philosophical principles of managing the socio-cultural sphere; innovative vectors of managing the socio-cultural sphere in modern conditions; sociocultural aspects of human resources management; main directions of development of marketing of socio-cultural institutions and organizations; components of creative economy; digitization of management processes in the field of culture, etc.

The participants of the event raised acute and debatable questions, reflected on the topics of current vectors of the development of modern socio-cultural management. In particular, professors of the Department of Fashion and Show Business of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts *Ya. Martynyshyn* and *O. Khlystun* emphasized the rapidity of changes taking place in modern society, its conflict and identified an epoch-making innovation that can smooth out the said confrontation – “the international movement for the dialogue of civilizations, under the auspices of the UN, which is guided by the principle of the need to recognize and respect the wealth of all civilizations without exception and to find the common ground that unites them for the sake of a comprehensive solution to all the problems facing humanity. In this regard, management culture can play an important role, especially understanding its cross-cultural aspects of international business communication and business behavior”.

The speakers raised the issue of professional self-fulfillment of the manager in the atmosphere of globalization, refusals, the need to make decisions in conditions of uncertainty, the transformation of the socio-cultural sphere and taking into account the multiculturalism of society, they emphasized the need for a thorough approach to the management of cultural organizations, taking into account the requirements of time management and digitalization of the

sphere, on the latest approaches to the effective management of the creative economy in the conditions of a full-scale invasion of russia, the relevance of popularizing Ukrainian culture at the international level (*O. Kalantaievska, O. Kostiuchenko, Ye. Kovalenko, I. Hardabkhadze, L. Butko, O. Darovanets, T. Povalii, N. Vorobiova, S. Fedorenko*); emphasized the importance during the crisis to make progress in the management of the socio-cultural sphere in the aspect of practical orientation (*O. Boiko, O. Krupa, K. Darovanets*).

It is important that crisis phenomena, one of the vivid examples of which is war, significantly affect the socio-cultural sphere, complicating the work of creative business, social institutions, and cultural space. However, the crisis is also a catalyst for evolution - the birth of new artistic forms, forms of communication, management methods, the search for new rules for institutions of the creative industry and culture (*A. Urbanskyi*), and an optimistic worldview, based on an understanding of the meaning and purpose of activity, reveals a creative attitude towards it, a desire to make it beautiful and harmonious for oneself and others, the most important factors determining the conditions for the formation of an optimistic worldview are the desire for self-improvement and humanism (*O. Kostiuchenko*).

The above shows that today there is also research into the quality of training future managers of the socio-cultural sphere, because despite the current problems of distance learning, a higher education student can fully obtain the necessary knowledge that can be transformed into separate competencies, and further – contribute to the formation of a competent specialist. The final success of this process directly depends on the quality of the educational and methodological complex developed by the scientific and pedagogical worker, as well as the conditions for obtaining the necessary knowledge (*T. Hryhorchuk*), because today requires the manager of the socio-cultural sphere to have systematic knowledge in humanitarian, cultural, legal, economic and managerial spheres, as well as a quick reaction to unpredictable processes – the ability to analyze, forecast, plan and quickly respond to challenges (*A. Urbanskyi*).

Wide interest of the participants of the conference was also aroused by the scientific explorations of higher education students on the problems of organizing the management of cultural institutions in modern conditions (*O. Bohuslavskyi, M. Burlaka, Ye. Verbetskyi, V. Lisovyk*), necessary qualities of a manager (*V. Hushko, A. Dakhno, L. Onufriichuk*), personal branding (*R. Zakharchenko*), marketing strategies of organizations (*S. Ratanina*), planing and development of projects (*M. Krasykova, A. Lytvynenko, R. Liakhova, O. Martynenko*), an effective combination of tradition and innovation (*A. Lytvynenko*), the current state of the domestic creative industry (*S. Pechkar, A. Pushmin*) and prospects for its development (*O. Murachov, O. Ovcharenko*) etc.

In general, the participants of the conference came to the conclusion that the efficiency and effectiveness of the activities of the organization in the field of culture in unstable conditions, which force all members of the organization to be constantly ready to respond to changes as a result of new circumstances and requests, depend to a large extent on the efficiency of its management.

Abstracts of the reports of all participants of the event were included in the collection of materials, which is presented in an online version on the website of the library of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts in free access.

Information about the Author:

Larysa Butko, Associate Professor, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, 20, Pershotravneva St., Kremenchuk 39600, Ukraine; e-mail: larysabutko@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8817-3381>